

Vinyl Copper(I) as Synthetic Reagent

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Recently organocopper reagents have attracted the attention of synthetic organic chemists because of their potential applications in organic syntheses¹⁻⁷. House *et al*⁸ have found methyl copper to be remarkably superior for conjugate addition to α , β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds. Based upon the reaction of methyl copper with different halides Corey and Posner⁹ have devised an elegant new general synthetic method for the attachment of methyl group to an alkyl, vinyl, allyl and aryl systems.

We now wish to report that vinyl copper reacts quite smoothly at 0° with a variety of organic halides and the presence of ester or ketonic group in the halide does not interfere. Our studies indicate that lithium divinyl copper is an excellent reagent for the selective replacement of Br or Cl atom in a wide variety of substrates by vinyl or substituted vinyl groups. Analogous to methyl copper which has been represented as $\text{Li}^+(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Cu}^-$, vinyl copper can be assigned the structure $\text{Li}^+(\text{R}_1\text{R}_2\text{C}=\text{CR}_3)_2\text{Cu}^-$. The reagent was prepared by the reaction of vinyl lithium in T.H.F.¹⁰ solution with dry cuprous iodide (molar ratio 2 : 1) at 0° under an atmosphere of nitrogen and most of the vinylations were performed below -5° with five moles of the copper reagent per mole of the halide derivative. The following chart illustrates the transformations which have been effected with the lithium divinyl copper reagent in tetrahydrofuran solution.

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In all cases products were chromatographed, distilled, and characterised by analytical data and comparison of their I. R. spectrum with the synthetic samples.

The synthetic method described above provides a simple approach to many substances hitherto accessible only by lengthy or complicated routes. It should be especially useful in the field of Terpenoids syntheses which have $\begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{array} \text{C}=\text{C}$ (isopropylidene) and $\begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{array} \text{C}$ (isopropenyl) groups in their structures.

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